

Original Research

Ranking Mutual Funds Performance Based on Post-modern Portfolio Theory Indicators Using Multi-Criteria Decision-Making Methods

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Abstract

Performance appraisal refers to the process of performance measurement, assessment, valuation, and judgement over time. Performance ranking based on several criteria of different values is possible only when multi-criteria decision models are adopted. In this regard, different indicators are used in accordance with the type of ranking. Accordingly, inspired by the support vector machine model (SVM) and the Promethee technique, the present study aimed to develop a performance appraisal model for mutual funds and rank them accordingly. In this study, 34 mutual funds accepted in Iran's capital market were selected during 2016-2018 using the systematic random sampling method. First, the key performance indicators were detected using the indicators of post-modern portfolio theory, which were then approved by managers, experts, and professionals. Then some information about each indicator was collected, and the experts and professionals' comments were used to weight the indicators and specify the importance and priority of each indicator. Afterwards, an applied model was developed to represent the indicators effective in ranking mutual funds. Finally, the SVM model and the Promethee technique were adopted to rank the concerned mutual funds. The findings revealed that, in comparison to the indicators of downside risk and Sortino, upside potential ratio has the greatest effect on the performance appraisal of the mutual funds accepted in Iran's capital market.

Keywords: Ranking, Downside risk, Sortino ratio, Upside potential, Mutual funds

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Introduction

Any organization is in an urgent need for a performance appraisal system to detect the desirability and quality of its operations, especially in complicated and dynamic environments. The non-existence of a performance appraisal system in an organization indicates the lack of communication with the internal and external organizational environment, resulting in the concerned organization's aging and eventual death (Abzari, 2008).

Performance appraisal in different companies is a challenging task as there is a set of different dimensions to be considered in the organization's performance appraisal. Furthermore, a large number of interests and different stakeholders should be regarded (Abzari, 2008).

Nowadays, given the competitive environment and changes in business conditions, credibility and level of acceptance are the most significant criteria for organizations. One of the main tools to represent this issue is ranking organizations/companies, which is an indicative of their credibility and power. Accordingly, many countries, including Iran, have ranked their companies in the capital market. Regarding the low efficiency of the ranking methods used in Iran's capital market, the adoption of a ranking method with high reliability is of paramount importance (Awan and Arshad, 2012).

Performance ranking considering several criteria of different values is possible only when multi-criteria decision models are adopted. In these models, different ratios are used proportionate to the type of ranking. Financial ratios are the most effective ratio to examine the company's performance and financial status (Chen et. Al., 2007).

In the modern theory, risk is defined as the total variability of the return portfolio around the return mean and is estimated by using variance. In other words, regarding the distribution of deviations in terms of variance, the modern portfolio theory considers similar weights for all positive and negative deviations under uncertainty conditions (upside and downside) as risks. This is why variance is recognized as a symmetric risk indicator and can be used when the distribution of returns is normal. This theory clearly distinguishes upside and downside fluctuations. In the post-modern portfolio theory, only fluctuations below the investor's target return rate are subject to risk; however, all other fluctuations beyond this target (under uncertainty conditions) are regarded as investment opportunities to reach the desired return rate (Chen et. Al., 2007).

Given today's competitive environment and changes in business conditions, credibility and level of acceptance are the most significant concerns for companies. In this regard, ranking is considered as one of the main tools to exhibits the companies' credibility and power. Accordingly, a majority of countries have ranked their companies on their stock exchanges. Regarding the low effectiveness of ranking methods used in Tehran Stock Exchange, the development of an effective ranking method with high reliability seems to be of paramount importance.

Performance ranking considering several criteria of different values is possible only when multi-criteria decision models are adopted. These methods utilize different

indicators in accordance with the type of ranking. Financial ratios are the most effective indicator of a company's performance and financial status. Accordingly, key performance indicators (using the post-modern portfolio theory indicators) were first detected and approved by managers, experts, and professionals. Some information about each of the indicators was then collected. Considering the experts and professionals' comments by weighting the indicators, the significance and priority of each indicator was determined. In the next step, an applied model was presented to reach proper indicators in ranking the mutual funds. Finally, the SVM model and the Promethee technique were adopted to rank the concerned mutual funds.

Theoretical foundations and research background

Another technique and strategy for capital-market liberalization is the establishment of country funds, which are divided into two groups with regard to the capital structure and financing: Open-end country funds and closed-end country funds

The country funds first issue some shares and spend the returns on buying some other shares in a foreign country. For example, Iran establishes a country fund and issues the shares of this fund in European countries and spend the proceeds to buy shares on the Tehran Stock Exchange.

The country fund was first adopted as a financial tool in Brazil in 1975 and was gradually utilized in other world markets following the awareness of other countries and with the contribution of the International Finance Institution. In South Korea, the first shares of the country fund were listed on the New York Stock Exchange in 1984. The achievements of Taiwan's country fund also made the country open its financial market to foreigners' direct investment. South Korea, Egypt, Thailand, Malaysia, Argentina, and Mexico are some other successful countries in this field (Ghalibafasl, 2013).

Mutual funds

Although the establishment of investment companies dates back to the eighteenth century in England, the first investment funds in were founded in 1924 in Boston, USA. Since then, mutual funds have continued to operate successfully worldwide, especially in the United States, accounting for a capital raise from \$ 448 million in 1940 to \$ 14 trillion by the end of 2003. Interestingly, the number of mutual funds in the United States also increased from 546 funds in 1980 to more than 8300 funds in 2001, accounting for about \$ 7,000 billion raise in assets by 2000. The total assets of the mutual funds in 1980, however, was only \$ 135 billion (Peltomaki, 2017).

Taking the significance of such funds into account, other countries have also established and developed such mutual funds. A mutual fund is a simple financial mediator allowing a group of investors to accumulate their money with the aim of investing under pre-specified conditions. The mutual fund has a manager, who is in charge of investing the returns raised from investment tools (usually stocks or bonds). When an individual invests in a fund, he/ she jointly owns a portion of the stock in the mutual fund. In other words, he/ she becomes a shareholder. The mutual fund certificate is one of the best financial tools since investment in the fund is simple and economical in

scale. In other words, individuals are not obliged to be involved in investment analysis; however, they simply rely on the experts in the field. Moreover, the accumulation of small capitals results in large capitals, as a productive factor in the capital market. In this regard, the greatest advantage of a mutual fund is the possibility of diversification, which refers to the idea of capital distribution among different investment tools with different ratios. The investment diversification significantly decreases risk. The mutual funds are founded to purchase different types of stocks, even hundreds or thousands of stocks. A person must spend some weeks to purchase different types of stocks, bonds, etc., thereby diversifying his portfolio. However, he/ she can do this during a few hours by purchasing a certificate or some shares of the mutual funds (Awan and Arshad, 2012).

This implies that investors not possessing sufficient expertise in the financial markets and not having enough opportunity to keep the price tack of various stocks and portfolios, can decrease one's risk by joining these mutual funds. Needless to note that most shareholders do not have sufficient knowledge in the capital market, and this has exposed them with many problems. In addition to reducing the investment risk, the mutual funds preserve the shareholders' assets and provides them with acceptable returns (Ghalibafasl, 2013).

Advantages of mutual fund

The main advantages of mutual funds are as follows:

1. One of the main advantages of the mutual funds (mainly with variable capital) is the potential to repurchase the fund's shares by the fund itself, which promotes their liquidity and place the investment units of these funds in the category of quasi-cash securities as an alternative to cash. Such liquidity is one of the major features provided to the financial system by the funds.

2. Another advantage of the mutual funds is the imposition of the same professional and specialized management to the funds of all investors (small or large, real or legal). In other words, the capital has no impact on the fund management since these funds are jointly invested in the stock exchange market.

3. The third advantage is the simple sales of the fund's investment units for investors since the fund itself is both the seller and the purchase of shares, and all funds perform their sales operations by announcing a free-of-charge phone number, in the absence of the investor, and by opening a special bank account for the investor. Since the investment units of mutual funds with variable capital are not traded in the stock market, they are not subject to time-consuming legal and administrative procedures to receive and pay funds, acquire shares, and so on.

4. Positives of diversification: According to the new portfolio theory, investment in a certain number of different stocks significantly decreases the investment risk. These funds reach this goal by investing in a wide range of stocks.

5. Positives of lower operating costs: Since the funds at the mutual fund's disposal are managed professionally in a large scale, they pose relatively lower transaction costs,

compared to individual investments, thereby leading to an increase in return on investment.

6. Positives of providing services to shareholders: Mutual funds provide highly proper services to investors, the main samples of which are reinvestment of funds, the payment of funds resulting from investments to shareholders at the earliest convenience, telephone sales, and quick and free-of-charge transfer of investors' funds among funds of a same family.

7. Ensuring managers' unethical measures: The devaluation of the investment is the only source of risk in the funds, and the probability of loss caused by fraud, financial scandal, or bankruptcy in such companies is almost equal to zero (Smith, 2014).

Introducing modern financial market theories

The modern financial theory dominated the world's academic forums and financial markets for more than half a century. In the 1980s and 1990s, some empirical evidence observed in the markets posed challenges to this theory. Recently, financial professionals have conducted many studies and research on this empirical evidence. They first spared their efforts to justify these cases using models in the modern financial theory. Some relevant studies are discussed below.

Post-modern investment theory and downside risk

The modern portfolio theory is explained with regard to the relationship between returns and risk calculated using the variance and standard deviation of returns. Post-modern portfolio theory (PMPT) also describes investor's behavior and specifies the optimal portfolio selection indicators with regard to the relationship between downside risk and returns. In other words, PMPT was developed based on the new model of downside risk and the resulting advancements.

PMPT is also considered as an appropriate measure to evaluate the portfolio performance, which offers more accurate and efficient indicators by using the downside risk indicator.

PMPT puts forth the substitution of financial assets, including money, stocks, currency, bank deposits, etc. at a micro level. A portfolio refers to an asset portfolio held by an investor maintaining a variety of different financial assets. Since individuals hold a combinations of cash, stocks, bank deposits, and bonds in their portfolio, changes in money supply, bank interest rates, etc. affects the demand for holding each of these components, including demand for stocks. This would in turn affect stock prices (Smith, 2014).

Some financial assets, such as bank deposits, have a stable, safe, risk-free return; however, the other assets such as stocks, have uncertain and risky returns.

Capital Asset Pricing Model (CAPM) is one of the most basic models to determine the optimal portfolio.

Assume that individuals' portfolios encompass two types of financial assets:

- 1) Financial assets with risky returns (stocks)
- 2) Financial assets with specified returns with no risk (bank deposit)

Each risky asset has a total random return $\bar{R}_i$ for $i=1, 2, \dots, n$, and an asset with specified returns has total return (i.e., $1 +$ a rate of return). First, the consumer has a wealth $\bar{W}$ and selects a percentage of his wealth as an asset i for investment. Accordingly, the consumer's wealth in the next period, when random returns are realized, is determined as follows:

$$\bar{W} = w \sum_{i=1}^n X_i R_i$$

Suppose that the consumer is to select X_i to maximize the expected utility of random wealth W . In this regard, the budget limit is determined as follows:

$$\sum_{i=1}^n X_i = 1$$

Since X_i is a percentage of consumer's wealth invested in the asset i , the sum of the invested percentages in all existing assets should be equal to one. This budget constraint is:

$$X_0 + \sum_{i=1}^n X_i = 1$$

Where, X_i is a percentage of financial wealth spent on financial assets with a certain return and contains no risk (bank deposit). So,

$$X_0 = 1 - \sum_{i=1}^n X_i$$

With replacing this phrase and its rearrangement, we have:

$$\bar{W} = w \left[X_0 R_0 + \sum_{i=1}^n X_i \bar{R}_i \right]$$

$$\bar{W} = w \left[\left(1 - \sum_{i=1}^n X_i \right) R_0 + \sum_{i=1}^n X_i \bar{R}_i \right]$$

$$\bar{W} = w \left[R_0 + \sum_{i=1}^n X_i (\bar{R}_i - R_0) \right]$$

With adjusting this budget constraint, we have the issue of maximizing constraints for $X_1, \dots, X_n$:

$$\text{Max} EU \left[w \left[R_0 + \sum_{i=1}^n X_i (\bar{R}_i - R_0) \right] \right]$$

The first-order conditions are obtained after deriving this expression:

$$EU'(\bar{W})(\bar{R}_i - R_0) = 0$$

The conditions are written as follows:

$$EU'(\bar{W})\bar{R}_i = R_0 EU'(\bar{W})$$

Using the covariance of random variables $\text{cov}(xy) = E(xy) - E(X)E(Y)$, this expression is converted as follows:

$$\text{COV}(U'(\bar{W}), R_i) + E\bar{R}_i EU'(\bar{W}) = R_0 EU'(\bar{W})$$

The following equation is reached from its rearrangement:

$$E\bar{R}_i = \frac{1}{EU'(\bar{W})} \text{COV}(U'(\bar{W}), \bar{R}_i)$$

The return of an asset is positively correlated with wealth and, on the other hand, risk aversion suggest that the ultimate utility is negatively correlated. This is,

$$\text{COV}(U'(\bar{W}), \bar{R}_i)$$

Accordingly, such an asset must have a higher expected return rate than the return of the risk-free financial assets in order to compensate for its risk. Thus, we have:

$$E\bar{R}_i = R_0 + \text{Risk Rewards (Donald, 2002)}.$$

Background of Studies

Qaragezlou and Moradi (2019) studied the effect of negative portfolio risk on stock price fluctuations and noticed that the standard deviation of shareholders' returns and the mean of shareholders' returns as independent variables affect stock price fluctuations. In other words, the standard deviation and mean of shareholders' returns affect stock price fluctuations.

Redeker and Wunderlich (2018) conducted portfolio optimization under dynamic risk constraints for continuous investment versus non-continuous investment. These

researchers obtained dynamic programming equations for random optimal control problems and solved them numerically. These numerical results indicate that the loss of portfolio returns is not large; however, the value at risk is significantly decreased. They then investigated the effects of time intervals and noticed that the loss of portfolio performance caused by the imposition of risky value constraints was usually more than the loss from improper investments.

Bayecote and Cuala (2018) studied corporate governance in the Turkish stock market using multi-criteria decision-making methods during 2007-2014. In their study, they used TOPSIS techniques, AHP method (hierarchical analysis), VIKOR method, and GRA method (gray analysis method) with regard to three indicators of leverage, profitability, and liquidity. The findings revealed the superiority of TOPSIS and AHP methods in corporate governance ranking.

Derakhshani et al. (2017) ranked insurance companies in North Khorasan Province using the TOPSIS method. The present study was to rank the insurance companies in North Khorasan Province during 2012 and 2013 based on the received premiums, the number of insurance policies, the number and the ratio of damages using the TOPSIS method. The required data were collected from the insurance companies of the province. Furthermore, AHP method was also used to weigh each indicator. According to the findings, Iran Insurance Company, as the only state insurance company, was ranked first among the other 13 insurance companies in the province during the concerned two-year period.

Mansouri and Bazargan (2016) ranked industrial and mining companies listed on the Tehran Stock Exchange using the fuzzy VIKOR technique. The findings indicated that, among the other criteria, profitability ratios with a coefficient of 0.354 and liquidity ratios with a coefficient of 0.154 had the most and the least significance in ranking companies, respectively. Metal Development Limited (Company) with an average ranking of 3 and Iran Manganese Mines Company with the ranking of 7 had the most and the least favorable conditions, respectively.

Namazi et al. (2017) examined a multi-criteria decision-making model for ranking companies listed on the Tehran Stock Exchange using balanced scorecard, stock market benchmarks, and Pairwise Rankings of all possible Alternatives (PAPRIKA) technique. The comparison of the explanatory power of ranking models based on separate criteria indicated the superiority of the balanced scorecard ranking model to the stock market criteria. Comparing the explanatory power of the ranking model based on combined criteria compared to the ones based on separate criteria also revealed the superiority of the former ones. In general, the findings suggested that, among the three ranking approaches, the combined ranking model with an adjusted coefficient of determination of 9.67% has higher explanatory power than other models. In contrast, there was no significant difference (Wong statistic: 0.04, $p=0.484$) between the adjusted coefficients of determination for the combined ranking model and the balanced scorecard ranking model (6.67%), indicating that the non-significant effect of Tehran Stock Exchange benchmarks in improving the ranking model. Accordingly, the context of the comprehensive ranking model results from the application of balanced scorecard criteria, and the combined model is the most favorable ranking model.

Arcan and Ander (2017) ranked insurance industry companies in Turkey using VIKOR method. Their findings indicated that two insurance companies (Hayat and Emeklilik) had the best performance ranking among other insurance companies.

Bahandri et al. (2014) investigated factors affecting performance by using financial ratios determining the financial performance in Nepal's commercial banks in a hierarchical analysis process.

Sun et al. (2017) developed a model for selecting an optimal stock portfolio, in which the stock portfolio selection problem is solved by the neural network after balancing mean-variance and skewness. The results highlighted the power of the model in solving the portfolio selection problem quickly.

In a study entitled "Combined MCDM techniques for exploring stock selection based on Gordon model", Lee et al. (2016) detected the factors affecting the stock price. In this study, they extracted the factors affecting the three key components of Gordon model in a review of the research literature.

Kanela and Kezalo (2015) used polynomial goal programming with regard to skewness to present the optimal stock portfolio in emerging markets. The findings confirmed the effectiveness of skewness in solving stock portfolio selection problems.

Bafghi et al. (2015) detected and ranked the factors affecting liquidity risk using a fuzzy multi-criteria decision-making approach (companies listed on the Tehran Stock Exchange). The findings revealed "demand deposits" with a weight of (0.04) in the third rank, "long-term deposits" with a weight of (0.07) in the seventh rank, "other deposits" with a weight of (0.02) in the first rank, "total deposits" with a weight of (0.04) in the fourth rank, "volume of bonds" with a weight of (0.09) in the ninth rank, "long-term investment" with a weight of (0.12) in the 11th rank, "growth of investments" with a weight of (0.10) in the 10th rank, "cash" with a weight of (0.05) in the fifth rank, "stock market value of the stock exchange" with a weight of (0.02) in the second rank, "payment facilities" with a weight of (0.06) in the sixth rank, "interval between assets and liabilities" with a weight of (0.19) in the 13th rank, "debt to the central stock exchange and other stock exchanges" with a weight of (0.08) in the 8th rank, and "financing cost" with a weight of (0.13) in the 12th rank.

In the study, Tai Liu (2014) examined fuzzy optimal portfolios. In his model, he considered the return on assets as fuzzy numbers. The study findings approved this financial and economic idea indicating that the higher the risk, the higher the potential return of an investment.

Bejourk et al. (2014) investigated portfolio optimization by combining the mean-variance model and risk aversion factor. They found out that modern portfolio theory was constrained by risk and returns, which always fail to reflect the realities of the investment markets (In the modern portfolio theory (mean-variance method), risk is calculated based on variance or its root (standard deviation)).

Chin Ta et al. (2009) adopted two mathematical approaches in their study entitled "Selecting Internet Company Stocks Using a Combined DEA and AHP approach". The

DEA and AHP approach was used to develop a framework for the stocks of 31 Internet companies in the US. The experimental results confirmed the effectiveness of the combined method, which encompasses performance analysis and structural decision making.

Research methodology

The statistical population of the present study encompassed all mutual funds listed in Iran's capital market (See Appendix). Since the research studies considered a limited sample, the researcher was to examine all mutual funds meeting the following inclusion criteria:

1. They were established before the study period.

2- From their establishment date to March 20, 2019, they were listed in the Tehran Stock Exchange.

3. Their required information is available by the aforementioned date.

With regard to the inclusion criteria, 34 mutual funds were selected as the study sample.

3.1. Support vector machine method

Suppose we have a set of data points $\{(x_1, c_1), (x_2, c_2), \dots, (x_n, c_n)\}$, and we are to divide them into two classes. Each x_i is a p -dimensional vector of real numbers, which are the variables expressing the software behavior.

Linear classification methods are to divide data by constructing a hypersurface (which is a linear equation). SVM, as one of the classification linear methods, detects the best hypersurface separating the data from the two classes at a maximum distance (Azar, 2013).

Promethee method

This method is one of the multi-criteria decision-making techniques and a ranking technique for a finite set of options, which should be ranked mostly based on contradictory criteria (Behzadian, 2009). Promethee 1 (partial ranking) and Promethee 2 (full ranking) were developed by G. B. Brans and first presented in 1982 at a conference at Laval University in Quebec, Canada (Brans et al., 1986). The information required for this model is quite transparent and understandable to analysts and decision makers, which can be divided into two categories:

-Inter-criteria information

- Intra-criterion information

Inter-criteria information is actually weights indicating the relative significance of different criteria. Weights are non-negative numbers and independent from the measurement unit of the criteria.

Regarding the intra-criterion information, it should be mentioned that the preference function in Promethee 2 is pairwise comparison. To this end, the deviation between the two alternatives of a particular criterion is considered, and this deviation is calculated in pairs for all the alternatives (Azar, 2013).

The Promethee method is used for the following problems (Brans et al., 1986):

$$\text{Max (Min) } \{f_1(a), f_2(a), f_k(a) \mid a \in A\}$$

Where, A represents the set of decision options, and

$f_j(a)$ and $j = 1, 2, 3, \dots, k$ is a set of indicators appraising the options.

Options are ranked by pairwise comparison of options in each indicator, which is measured using a predefined preference function at the range of [0 and 1]. For a preference function P , we have the options a and b and the index j :

$$P_j(a,b) = P_j[d_j(a,b)]$$

As

$d_j(a,b) = f_j(a) - f_j(b)$ represents the differences of dimensions in j .

In the next step, the overall preference of each alternative in comparison to the other alternatives is calculated for all indicators by considering the weight of each criterion. For example, for a and b , as two alternatives from the set A , we have:

$$\pi(a,b) = \sum_{j=1}^k P_j(a,b)w_j$$

$$\pi(b,a) = \sum_{j=1}^k P_j(b,a)w_j$$

This is done for all alternatives in pairs. In the set A , each alternative a is exposed to $(n-1)$ alternatives. Accordingly, two ranking flows are defined as follows:

$$\phi^+(a) = \frac{1}{n-1} \sum_{x \in A} \pi(a,x)$$

The positive preference flow indicates how much the given option a is superior to the other options, implying the strength of the option a . The largest $\phi^+(a)$ shows the best option. The degree of preference for the other options to the options a , which is called input flow, is calculated as follows:

$$\phi^-(a) = \frac{1}{n-1} \sum_{x \in A} \pi(x,a)$$

The negative preference flow indicates how much the other options are superior to the given option a , implying the weakness of the option a . The smallest $\phi^-(a)$ represents the best option (azar, 2013).

Partial ranking in a Promethee (PI, II, RI) is obtained from positive and negative preference rankings. Both flows do not usually contain identical rankings, and Promethee is their partial ranking.

$$(aP^I b) \text{ if } \begin{cases} \phi^+(a) > \phi^+(b) & , & \phi^-(a) < \phi^-(b) \\ \phi^+(a) > \phi^+(b) & , & \phi^-(a) = \phi^-(b) \\ \phi^+(a) - \phi^+(b) & , & \phi^-(a) < \phi^-(b) \end{cases}$$

$$(aI^I b) \text{ if } \phi^+(a) = \phi^+(b) \quad , \quad \phi^-(a) = \phi^-(b)$$

$$(aP^I) \text{ otherwise}$$

Where, PI, II, and RI represent preferences, indifferences, and incomparability, respectively (Brans & Marshall, 1986).

- In $aPIb$, the highest strength a is associated with the lowest weakness, indicating that option a is superior to option b .

- In $aIIb$, both positive and negative ranking flows are equal.

- In $aRIb$, the highest strength of an option is associated with the lowest weakness of another option (Azar, 2012).

Accordingly, the options are incomparable. This usually occurs when option a is strong in a set of criteria in which option b is weak, option b in other criteria is stronger than the option a . In this case, the options are incomparable, and the method fails to rank them. The decision-maker, however, can rank options at his own discretion.

A decision maker always looks for complete ranking since decision making is less challenging in this case. The calculation of the net ranking flow makes this possible (azar, 2013):

$$\phi(a) = \phi^+(a) - \phi^-(a)$$

This flow results from balance between positive and negative ranking flows. A higher net flow represents the superior option. This is a version of the Promethee 2 method; hence, the complete ranking by the Promethee 2 method is as follows:

$$(aP^{II} b) \text{ if } \phi(a) > \phi(b)$$

$$(aI^{II} b) \text{ if } \phi(a) = \phi(b)$$

In this case, all options are comparable, and no option is incomparable.

Regarding this statistical model and the research objectives of the, the following hypotheses were formulated:

H 1. Downside risk has the greatest effect on the performance appraisal of mutual funds accepted in Iran's capital market.

H 2. Sortino ratio has the greatest effect on the performance appraisal of mutual funds accepted in Iran's capital market.

H 3. Upside potential ratio the greatest effect on the performance appraisal of mutual funds accepted in Iran's capital market.

Research variables

Dependent variable :

Performance and ranking: These two variables were calculated using Promethee technique and SVM method.

Independent variables:

Downside risk: In this study, the following equation was used to measure the downside risk:

$$LPM^2 = \frac{1}{m} \sum_{t=1}^m [Min(0, (h - R))]^2$$

Where, h represents the target return, R is the fund's return, and m stands for the number of observations.

Sortino ratio: This indicator is calculated as follows:

$$SR = \frac{R_p - MAR}{DR}$$

Where, MAR represents the minimum acceptable rate of return and DR represents the downside risk. This theory uses the concept 'downside risk' to measure risk. This concept is one of the advancements of the 1990s in the field of risk measurement.

Upside potential ratio: According to the post-modern portfolio theory, another performance appraisal indicator is the upside potential ratio. This indicator, developed by Sortino, Van Der Meer, and Plantinga (1999), is calculated by dividing the ratio of upside potential or the expected return to MAR by the downside risk (Sortino, 2001):

$$UPR = \frac{\sum_{t=1}^T t^+ \frac{1}{T} (R - MAR)}{\left[\sum_{t=1}^T t^- \frac{1}{T} (R - RAM)^2 \right]^{\frac{1}{2}}}$$

Where, R is the rate of return, and T is the number of MARs, the minimum acceptable rate of return by the investor, and is equivalent to the risk-free rate of return.

Research results

Descriptive statistics of research

Table 1 presents central tendency indicators such as mean and dispersion indicators such as standard deviation, kurtosis, and skewness.

Table 1 Descriptive statistics of research variables

Variables	F	Mean	Median	Mode	Sg	Variance	Kurtosis	Skewness	Variation scope
Downside risk	102	1.37912	1.35915	.688 ^a	.308491	.095	1.409	4.843	1.991
Sortino	102	1.00804	.95255	.504 ^a	.266923	.071	1.301	2.594	1.399
Upside potential	102	.75343	.67607	1.593	.548491	.301	1.002	1.292	2.640

The research variables are calculated annually. In this study, 34 mutual funds were included, so $3 * 34 = 202$. Here, 34 is the number of mutual funds in the study sample, and 3 indicates the research period (2016-2018). Accordingly, there were 102 years/fund observations for each variable. If the mean and median values of the variables are close, the variables are distributed symmetrically. This is an important feature since symmetry is one of the properties of the normal distribution, which is discussed in the following section (Kurtosis and skewness of the normal distribution are zero). Table 1 presents the descriptive statistics of variables, including mean, median, minimum observations, maximum observations, and standard deviation of mutual funds with regard to the 34 indicators of the post-modern portfolio theory. In the study of the statistical population distribution, the representative value around which the other values are distributed is called central tendency. Any numerical criterion representing the data set center is called the central tendency criterion. Mean and median are the most common measure of center tendency.

The main measure of central tendency is mean, which is the central point of distribution and is an appropriate measure to show the data centrality. For example, the mean of the downside risk ratio is 1.37912, implying that most of the data related to this variable are concentrated around this point. Media is another central tendency measure, which shows the state of the research sample in statistics and the probability theory.

Standard deviation is a measure of dispersion and shows how far the data are from the mean on average. If the standard deviation of a set of data is close to zero, the data are close to the mean and their scatteredness is little. In contrast, large standard deviation

values show the significant dispersion of data. Standard deviation is equal to the square root of variance, and its advantage, compared to variance, is that it has as many dimensions as the data. To put in simple words, standard deviation is a measure of the scatteredness of observations around the mean. As presented in Table 1, the standard deviation values of the variables were not zero, and they met this condition. Among the statistical population under study, the maximum and minimum values of this parameter were .548491 (upside potential ratio) and .266923 (Sortino ratio), respectively.

Weighting the ratios and determining the significance of each indicator

In this section, according to the experts' comments, pairwise comparisons were run between variables, and their weight percentages were then determined using Expert Choice software. A matrix preference questionnaire was developed to obtain the weight percentages. The variables were listed in the columns and rows of the matrix in this questionnaire, and the experts and professionals (n=5) were asked to determine the priority of each variable, compared to the other variables, using a scoring scale ranging from 1 to 9. Finally, the mean was calculated Table 2. The resulting matrix is a compatible matrix, in which each of the matrix arrays is a triangular fuzzy number. In the next step, Chang's method was used to weight each ratio. The pairwise comparison matrices and the weight of each ratio are presented below. First, the pairwise comparison matrix and the weights of the indicators were calculated, and then the weights of the sub-ratios of each major ratio were estimated as well.

Table 2 Pairwise comparison matrix of research variables

Ratios	C ₁	C ₂	C ₃
C ₁	1	1/2	1/5
C ₂	2	1	1/3
C ₃	5	3	1
Total	8	4.5	1.53

Where,

C1: Downside risk indicator

C2: Sortino ratio

C3: Upside potential ratio

Table 3. Normalized pairwise comparison matrix of variables

Ratios	C ₁	C ₂	C ₃	Weight vector
C ₁	0.125	0.111	0.130	0.122
C ₂	0.250	0.222	0.218	0.230
C ₃	0.625	0.667	0.654	0.647

As present in Table 3, after normalizing the pairwise comparison matrix, the upside potential ratio with a weight percentage of 64.7% was the most significant variable from the respondents' perspective. The lowest preference level was related to the Sortino ratio with a weight percentage of 12%. According to the obtained weight vector, the effectiveness of the ratios can be arranged as follows:

$$C_1 < C_2 < C_3$$

After calculating the indicators for each mutual fund during 2016-2019, preliminary decision matrices were formed. After Euclidean normalization, the matrices were multiplied by the weights corresponding to each indicator of the postmodern portfolio theory. Then the preliminary normal weighted matrices were formed to be included in the two ranking methods, namely SVM and the Promethee. The final weight was obtained from the weight mean of each indicator in comparison to the other ones.

After calculating all the values for the three ratios, the final decision was tabulated to rank the mutual funds.

Ranking options using SVM and Promethee methods

The mutual funds were ranked using SVM and Promethee methods with regard to the final Decision Table obtained at the end of the previous step.

Ranking by the Promethee method

In this section, the problem was ranked using the Promethee method. Due to the limitations in scope, the details are not presented, and only the final ranking is discussed.

As it was mentioned, 34 companies of the mutual funds were ranked using three indicators of downside risk ratio, Sortino ratio, and upside potential ratio. Each mutual fund was ranked based on these indicators and then weighted. After calculations, the rankings were determined by using decision-making techniques.

A preference function is need to have ranking in the Promethee method. This preference function is determined by comparing the significance and priority of the options. Accordingly, a normal criterion is considered for the preference function since we want all options to have equal points.

To have complete ranking, the perimeter method should be used, for which the flows $\phi + (a)$ and $\phi - (a)$ and then $\phi(a)$ need to be calculated. Finally, the option with larger ϕ is selected as the best option.

Ranking by SVM

A preference function is also needed to perform the SVM ranking. This preference function is determined by comparing the significance and priority of the options. Accordingly, a normal criterion is considered for the preference function since we want all options to have equal points.

To have complete ranking, SVM should be used, for which the flows $\phi + (a)$ and $\phi - (a)$ and then $\phi(a)$ need to be calculated. Finally, the option with larger ϕ is selected as the best option.

Combined ranking using arithmetic mean

To combine rankings and reach a single ranking Table, the rankings of each of the companies must be combined using combination methods. To this end, the arithmetic mean was used and three ranking Tables were obtained for the 2016, 2017, and 2018. The results of the combined rankings for the mutual funds accepted in Iran's capital market are as follows:

Table 4 Combined ranking by mutual funds 'arithmetic mean in 2016

Final Ranking	Promethee	SVM	Arithmetic Mean
Rahnama Mutual Fund	23	28	26
Sinai Mutual Fund	22	18	20
Dey Insurance Mutual Fund	8	20	14
Naghsh-e-Jahan Mutual Fund	15	17	16
Arg-e-Houman Mutual Fund	25	16	21
Omid Iranian Mutual Fund	34	34	34
Apadana Mutual Fund	10	13	12
Pishroo Mutual Fund	20	32	26
Tadbirgar-e-Sarmayeh Mutual Fund	21	23	22
Tadbirgaran-e- Farda Mutual Fund	12	10	11
Firouzeh Mutual Fund	26	30	28
Karafarian-e-Bartar Ayandeh Mutual Fund	6	5	6
Amin Karafarin Mutual Fund	13	25	19

Final Ranking	Promethee	SVM	Arithmetic Mean
Isatis Mutual Fund	18	15	17
Eghtesad Novin Bank Mutual Fund	1	1	1
Maskan Bank Mutual Fund	17	8	13
Boors-24 Mutual Fund	9	7	8
Borsiran Mutual Fund	3	6	5
Pasargad Mutual Fund	28	19	24
Pouya Mutual Fund	2	2	2
Khobregan Mutual Fund	31	26	29
Razavi Mutual Fund	14	21	18
Refah Mutual Fund	5	22	14
Sahm Ashena Mutual Fund	30	29	30
Shakhes Karafarin Mutual Fund	4	4	4
Saba Mutual Fund	16	12	14
San'at-O-Ma'dan Mutual Fund	33	33	33
Farabi Mutual Fund	32	31	32
Tejarat Bank Kargozarin Mutual Fund	29	27	28
Caspian Mehr Iranian Mutual Fund	11	3	7
Momtaz Mutual Fund	27	24	26
Noe-Andishan Mutual Fund	7	11	9
Novin Mutual Fund	19	14	17
Tadbirgaran-e Agah Mutual Fund	24	9	17

Table 5 Combined ranking by mutual funds 'arithmetic mean in 2017

Final Ranking	Promethee	SVM	Arithmetic Mean
Rahnama Mutual Fund	24	30	27
Rahnama Mutual Fund	26	24	25
Dey Insurance Mutual Fund	20	23	22
Naghsh-e-Jahan Mutual Fund	23	22	23

Final Ranking	Promethee	SVM	Arithmetic Mean
Arg-e-Houman Mutual Fund	28	20	24
Omid Iranian Mutual Fund	11	1	6
Apadana Mutual Fund	13	17	15
Pishroo Mutual Fund	30	7	19
Tadbirgar-e-Sarmayeh Mutual Fund	9	27	18
Omid Iranian Mutual Fund	21	18	20
Firouzeh Mutual Fund	29	34	32
Karafarian-e-Bartar Ayandeh Mutual Fund	10	8	9
Amin Karafarin Mutual Fund	8	29	19
Isatis Mutual Fund	15	13	14
Eghtesad Novin Bank Mutual Fund	18	14	16
Maskan Bank Mutual Fund	17	12	15
Boors-24 Mutual Fund	4	4	4
Borsiran Mutual Fund	7	9	8
Pasargad Mutual Fund	31	21	26
Pouya Mutual Fund	5	10	8
Khobregan Mutual Fund	1	32	17
Razavi Mutual Fund	25	26	26
Refah Mutual Fund	12	25	19
Sahm Ashena Mutual Fund	2	33	18
Shakhes Karafarin Mutual Fund	6	6	6
Saba Mutual Fund	16	15	16
San'at-O-Ma'dan Mutual Fund	3	3	3
Farabi Mutual Fund	33	2	18
Tejarat Bank Kargozarin Mutual Fund	34	31	33
Caspian Mehr Iranian Mutual Fund	14	5	10
Momtaz Mutual Fund	32	28	30
Noe-Andishan Mutual Fund	23	19	21

Final Ranking	Promethee	SVM	Arithmetic Mean
Novin Mutual Fund	19	16	18
Tadbirgaran-e Agah Mutual Fund	27	11	19
Rahnama Mutual Fund	7	29	8
Sinai Mutual Fund	31	19	26
Dey Insurance Mutual Fund	5	21	8
Naghsh-e-Jahan Mutual Fund	1	17	17
Arg-e-Houman Mutual Fund	25	14	26
Omid Iranian Mutual Fund	12	34	19
Apadana Mutual Fund	2	13	18
Pishroo Mutual Fund	6	31	6

Table 6 Combined ranking by mutual funds 'arithmetic mean in 2018

Final Ranking	Promethee	SVM	Arithmetic mean
Rahnama Mutual Fund	7	29	8
Sinai Mutual Fund	31	19	26
Dey Insurance Mutual Fund	5	21	8
Naghsh-e-Jahan Mutual Fund	1	17	17
Arg-e-Houman Mutual Fund	25	14	26
Omid Iranian Mutual Fund	12	34	19
Apadana Mutual Fund	2	13	18
Pishroo Mutual Fund	6	31	6
Tadbirgar-e-Sarmayeh Mutual Fund	23	23	26
Tadbirgaran-e- Farda Mutual Fund	22	11	21
Firouzeh Mutual Fund	8	30	15
Karafarian-e-Bartar Ayandeh Mutual Fund	15	3	16
Amin Karafarin Mutual Fund	25	24	20
Isatis Mutual Fund	34	8	34
Eghtesad Novin Bank Mutual Fund	10	9	12

Final Ranking	Promethee	SVM	Arithmetic mean
Maskan Bank Mutual Fund	20	10	26
Boors-24 Mutual Fund	21	4	22
Borsiran Mutual Fund	12	7	12
Pasargad Mutual Fund	26	18	28
Pouya Mutual Fund	6	5	5
Khobregan Mutual Fund	13	25	19
Razavi Mutual Fund	18	22	13
Refah Mutual Fund	1	20	5
Sahm Ashena Mutual Fund	17	28	14
Shakhes Karafarin Mutual Fund	9	6	7
Saba Mutual Fund	3	12	5
San'at-O-Ma'dan Mutual Fund	28	32	23
Farabi Mutual Fund	2	33	4
Tejarat Bank Kargozarin Mutual Fund	31	27	28
Caspian Mehr Iranian Mutual Fund	14	1	18
Momtaz Mutual Fund	5	26	13
Noe-Andishan Mutual Fund	30	16	29
Novin Mutual Fund	19	15	17
Tadbirgaran-e Agah Mutual Fund	24	2	13

Conclusions and Suggestions

The increasing development of mutual funds over the last few decades implies that they, as a new investment institution, are welcomed by investors. Both the rise of capital markets and the need for knowledge and expertise to have safe investment resulted in the emergence of various types of funds, including mutual funds, hedge funds, and others. Although the establishment of the mutual funds dates back to the eighteenth century in England, the first modern mutual funds were founded in 1924 in Boston, USA. Since then, these mutual funds have expanded worldwide as such there has been an upward trend for the number of these funds worldwide. In this case, the number of the mutual funds raised from 51671 funds in 2000 to 66350 funds by the end of 2007, thereby promoting their attractiveness for investors and enhancing their success in the capital markets (Stock Exchange and Securities Organization, 2010, 12). Although Iranian mutual funds have no history as old as the mutual funds in other countries, this new

financial institution has remarkably grown as more than 100 mutual funds initiated their operation in Iran's capital market over a short term. Mutual funds are exploited in world stock exchanges with the aim of promoting investment efficiency and prosperity in capital markets and play a critical role in equipping financial resources and directing them toward production capacities. The major philosophy underpinning these funds is to raise funds to be invested in a variety of securities (e.g., stocks, bonds, etc.). Given the high volume of their sales in the capital market, the efficiency of these funds is one of the hotbeds of debates. Accordingly, the present study sought to detect, appraise, and rank the performance of mutual funds based on the postmodern portfolio theory indicators by using multi-criteria decision-making methods. In other words, the main objective of this study is to appraise the efficiency and performance of the listed companies and to rank them using the SVM model and the Promethee technique. Regarding the nature of the study, no independent or dependent variable was specified in the present research; however, the preliminary indicators were extracted after consulting some experts and studying and reviewing their comments. These indicators were then weighted and their values were determined.

Ranking companies in Iran's capital market is considered as a measure promoting market efficiency and a useful guide for investors and market activists. This would also enhance market competition and develop capital markets.

1. Considering the rejection of the first research hypothesis with an effective percentage of 12.2%, it is inferred that investors have paid less attention to the downside risk in ranking and in stock trading and investment. This indicator should be of greater concern in ranking mutual funds.

2. Considering the rejection of the second research hypothesis with an effective percentage of 23%, it is inferred that there has been rising positive attention to the Sortino ratio in ranking during the study period. Consequently, investors have paid more positive attention to this ratio in trading and investment. In other words, there has been an increasing attention to the competitive status, value, and calculation of the Sortino ratio and the fund's overall performance in investment. Investors, shareholders, and industries are hence suggested to consider the Sortino ratio.

3. Considering the acceptance of the third research hypothesis with an effective percentage of 64.8%, it is inferred that, during the studied years, the upside potential has been of greater concern in ranking and investment, compared to the other indicators. In other words, this indicator is considered a basis for individual investments. Accordingly, to adopt competitive measures with the aim of further transparency, fund managers are suggested not only to calculate and announce the modern portfolio theory indicators (e.g., Sharpe ration and market beta) but also to appraise the fund's performance based on other indicators, in which the risk factor is included. They should also present the collected information to the investors and stakeholders via the fund's website.

Investors are also recommended to consider not only the variations in a fund's returns but also the upside investment potential of the fund and to utilize efficient benchmarks such as postmodern portfolio theory indicators to appraise the fund's performance.

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